

Preparing the Research & Innovation Core for Mission Ocean, Seas & Waters

Deliverable D1.3

Data Management Plan

V1.0

GA No. 101056957 - PREP4BLUE

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www.PREP4BLUE.eu

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1. Introduction

1.1. Executive Summary

1.1.1. Objective

The PREP4BLUE Data Management Plan (DMP) outlines the policies and procedures to be followed by the PREP4BLUE consortium for managing the data generated and collected during and after the project. It should serve as a manual for all data management procedures to be followed in the PREP4BLUE project while also providing background information and rationale for each procedure in the context of Horizon Europe.

1.1.2. Rationale

PREP4BLUE will collect data, develop algorithms and models to automatize data collection, enrichment and analysis. All data generated will be FAIR and made publicly available. Building on existing open science resources and Horizon Europe guidelines, the PREP4BLUE DMP outlines protocols and policies to manage and standardise the consortium's approach to the collection and storage of data, and ensuring this data is accessible and reusable within the terms of the project Grant Agreement (GA) and Consortium Agreement (CA).

This DMP will include measures to ensure PREP4BLUE complies with the requisite open access, while taking into account the need to balance this openness with the protection of scientific information, commercialisation and Intellectual Property Rights (IPR), privacy concerns and security. These policies are also reflected in [Annex 5 of the AGA](#).

1.1.3. Principles and Protocols

The PREP4BLUE DMP is to be used as a reference document by partners in order to ensure compliance with both internal project and external EU rules and regulations. This section will first provide a clear and easily-accessible summary of the **Key Principles** and **Protocols** which all partners are obliged to follow. The sections that follow provide further context and detailed explanations outlining the necessity of the established protocols.

It is the responsibility of every partner to ensure they understand and follow the protocols established in this document. Protocols have been summarised under the following headings:

- Data Management
- Ensuring Data Findability
- Ensuring Data Accessibility and Reusability

KEY PRINCIPLES & PROTOCOL - Data Management

- The **organisation and formatting of data collected will be the responsibility of the relevant data-owner**, which must be in line with the accepted standards in the respective field, overseen by Task Leaders. This includes formatting and metadata. PREP4BLUE aims to make data ingestion automated and FAIR (see below), and this should be the focus for all data owners.
- **Each partner is responsible for ensuring the security of their datasets.** To avoid losses, partners must take measures to ensure that data are backed-up using reliable methods. Partners are advised to consult with their organisation IT professionals to set up and manage data security and make sure the right safeguards are in place.
- From the start of each relevant task, project partners should consider identifying the most suitable file types and structures to be used to support external interoperability once ready and published where appropriate.

Best practices indicated hereafter should be followed by individuals involved in the project's research outputs and generating data.

1. When relevant, register at ORCID: <http://orcid.org> which provides a consistent identity for individuals.
2. Follow prior notice procedures as outlined in the sections 8 and 9 in the PREP4BLUE Plan for Dissemination, Exploitation and Communication (PDEC)¹.
3. Ensure that EC funding is acknowledged, including the project name and GA number (see section 2.2.4 and the PDEC for official text to use or contact ERINN, cliona@erinn.eu).
4. Ensure that peer-reviewed scientific publications based on PREP4BLUE results are published in Open Access (e.g. Gold or Green) (See PDEC).
5. Submit data underlying the published peer-reviewed scientific publications to the Coordinating Team (IFREMER with support by EuroMarine and ERINN) for evaluation.
6. When submitting these data, if a partner already intends to protect the data (see section 2.1.3.2), they should communicate this to the Coordinating Team to ensure an optimum level of confidentiality is upheld from the earliest stage.
7. Once cleared by the Coordinating Team, or if no objection is raised within 10 working days of receipt, ensure that data underlying published peer-reviewed scientific publications are deposited in an appropriate open-access data repository no later than 1 month after publication.

PROTOCOL – Findability

For each dataset collected or generated through PREP4BLUE, partner should consider the following, **Open-Access repository requirements** (for *all* data approved for open-access):

1. Researchers have authority to select their repository of choice. Where possible it should be domain specific. In order to facilitate linkages, the suggested repository is [Zenodo](#), but if that is not applicable consider the following:
 - a. The PREP4BLUE Mission Ecosystem Database, once running, may be used as suggested OA repository for PREP4BLUE; if appropriate. The data will be made available through the cloud services of the eScience Centre at SDU (UCloud, DEiC EOSC-Nordic initiatives).
 - b. Use an external data archive or repository already established for your research domain to preserve the data according to recognised standards in your discipline. You may search for data repositories (see the non-exhaustive list of suggested repositories in [Annex I](#)).
 - c. Or if available, use an institutional research data repository, or your research group's established data management facilities.
 - d. Or use a cost-free data repository.
2. Ensure the chosen online repository facilitates the identification of data and refers to standard identification mechanisms (ideally persistent and unique identifiers such as Digital Object Identifiers (DOIs)).
3. The organisation and formatting of data collected will be the responsibility of the relevant data-owner.

¹ Beneficiaries that intend to disseminate their results must give advance notice (prior notice) to the other beneficiaries, unless agreed otherwise, at least 15 calendar days advance notice to other beneficiaries (unless agreed otherwise), together with sufficient information on the results they will disseminate.

Any other beneficiary may object within (unless agreed otherwise) 15 days of receiving notification, if it can show that its legitimate interests in relation to the results or background would be significantly harmed. In such cases, the results may not be disseminated unless appropriate steps are taken to safeguard those interests.

Notwithstanding the above, certain dissemination activities which, by their nature, must be carried out in a timely manner (e.g. social media posts, promotional articles and reports) will be exempt from the obligation to give prior notice to all partners so as not to impede the project's dissemination strategy, provided that all PREP4BLUE beneficiaries engaged in such dissemination are in agreement prior to such dissemination and provided that the duty of confidentiality is respected (GA Article 13).

4. Each data-owner will be responsible for depositing relevant data in the appropriate repository.
5. Ensure that research outputs and datasets are cross-referencing each other (e.g. scientific publications and the data behind them).
6. Outline the discoverability of the data (give metadata provision). Each dataset owner will ensure that their chosen repositories disseminate (meta)data to OpenAIRE to maximise data sharing, finding and re-use of research outputs from PREP4BLUE (see section 2.2.).

PROTOCOL – Accessibility and Reusability

Prior notice and confidentiality review

- Although not obligatory, in the interest of FAIR data PREP4BLUE partners are encouraged to make any other project datasets that do not require protection – regardless of whether they are connected to a publication – available open-access.
- Information on all datasets must be entered into the Data Plan Inventory which will be made available on the PREP4BLUE TEAMS.
- Whenever information on a new dataset is uploaded to the PREP4BLUE TEAMS, or a previously created dataset is changed in such a way as might alter its protection level, the partner primarily responsible for the dataset must notify the Project Coordination team (IFREMER with the support of EuroMarine and ERINN).
 - If a partner intends to protect any data, they should communicate this to the Project Coordination team to ensure an optimum level of confidentiality is upheld from the earliest stage.
 - Any evidence of applications for protection and/or associated legal processes relating to said dataset should be sent to the Project Coordination team within six months of this notification.
- If no evidence of protection is provided, the Project Coordination team may request that data be made accessible.
- The Project Coordination team will provide feedback on the type of protection mechanism, if any, they believe should be applied to the data.
- If a dataset is deemed suitable for open access, the Project Coordination team will inform the data owner and request they submit information on their data to the Coordinating Team for evaluation. If cleared by the Coordinating Team, or if no objection is raised within 10 working days of receipt, the data owner is responsible for uploading it to an appropriate open-access repository within 30 days of Coordinating Team approval (see below for repository requirements).
- If a dataset is deemed to be unsuitable for open access, the data owner may still be required to place relevant metadata in a suitable repository, providing said metadata does not itself constitute a protection breach.

When considering the potential to make data open access, **partners are requested to review the PREP4BLUE CA (Consortium Agreement)**. This defines the main approach regarding the ownership, protection and access to key knowledge like Intellectual Property (IP) and data. This approach will allow the PREP4BLUE partners, collectively and individually, to pursue opportunities arising from the project's results. Some of the major aspects covered in the CA are briefly summarized below:

- **Confidentiality:** Each partner will treat information from other partners as confidential unless otherwise stated and not disclose it to third parties unless the information is publicly available.

- **Results-/ Background-/ Data- owners** will notify the partnership of their planned intent to upload datasets to open-access repositories following the same prior notice procedure as is set up for publication of results (45 days).
- **Pre-existing Know How:** Each partner is, and remains, the sole owner of its IPR over its Pre-existing Know-How. The partners have identified and listed in the CA the Pre-Existing Know-How over which they may grant access rights for the project. The partners agree that the Access Rights to the Pre-existing Know-How needed for carrying out their own work under the project shall be granted on a royalty-free basis.
- **Ownership and Protection of Results:** The ownership of results will belong to the partner(s) generating the results. Protection will be implemented appropriately. When the result is the outcome of work carried out by two or more partners and their respective share of the work cannot be ascertained, joint ownership will be agreed between the partners as it is established in the CA Article 8.2. If a partner wishes to assign any knowledge to a third party, they should do so while observing the conditions set out in the Prep4Blue GA, especially articles 8, 9, 10, and should inform the other partners and request their consent, which should not unreasonably be withheld.
- **Access Rights:** Partners grant to each other royalty-free access rights to knowledge generated in the project and to the background knowledge they bring to the project to the extent needed to successfully perform the project tasks allocated to them (see CA article 9).
- **Patents:** Under Article 16.4 and Annex 5 of the GA, partners who own knowledge suitable for patent are obliged to make applications for patents or similar form of protection and shall supply details of such application to the other partners. Information relating to patents that have been registered must be submitted under the 'IPR' section of the EU Funding and Tender Opportunities Portal.
- **Use and Dissemination:** If dissemination of knowledge does not adversely affect its protection or use and subject to legitimate interests, the partners shall ensure further dissemination of their own knowledge as provided under the GA (see Article 17) which has been signed by all partners.

1.1.4. Revision history and plan

The DMP operates as a functional manual and will be updated over the course of the project whenever significant changes arise, such as:

- New types of data
- Changes in consortium policies
- Changes in consortium composition and external factors

As new data are generated, they will be logged in the format of the Data Inventory Table in the PREP4BLUE TEAMS by the data owner.

The PREP4BLUE DMP will also be reviewed and updated for the DMP Update Report (D1.7) due in M18 (Nov 2023) and again for a final update (D1.10) in M36 (May 2025). Each update will be validated by the full consortium. Changes will be recorded in Table 1 (below) to support clarity and transparency in the revision process. At this stage we foresee the following updates/ changes.

Deliverable (D)	Date	Revised by	Reason
D1.3 - DMP	M6 - 30.11.22	ERINN	Establish the PREP4BLUE approach for the project data management plan.
D1.7 - DMP update	M18 – 30.11.23	ERINN	Define Data-sets, using the Data Inventory Template.
D1.10 - Final DMP	M36 – 30.05.24	ERINN	Impact analysis of the DMP

Table 1. Timeline for the review of the PREP4BLUE DMP

2. DMP Approach

2.1 Open Innovation in the European Union

Open Science permits knowledge to circulate more quickly and to be more freely available; it does not mean 'free science'. It is essential to ensure that intellectual property is protected before making knowledge publicly available. This enables subsequent attraction of investments that can help translate research results into innovation. If this is taken into account, fuller and wider access to scientific publications and research data can help accelerate innovation. The potential benefits of opening up research information are clearly recognised in the European Commission's investment plan for Europe where it is stated that in order to '*boost research and innovation, EU competitiveness would benefit from fewer barriers to knowledge transfer, open access to scientific research and greater mobility of researchers*' (COM (2014) 903 final).

Starting with the Evolution of Open Science within the EC - the journey began in FP7 in 2008: Open Access (OA) Pilot: Grantees were asked to deposit copies of their publications into digital repositories which allowed open access.

In 2014, H2020 began, and OA became mandatory, and the Open Research Data Pilot (ORDP) was introduced – data was to be made open access and data management plans were introduced as a deliverable.

Half-way through H2020 the ORDP became the default position for all grantees. It was expected that all projects would participate in making the data supporting their publications open -during GA negotiations you could provide justification to not participate.

The following scheme shows the evolution of Open Science Policy across FPs.

Figure 1 Evolution of open science policy across FPs

For explanations and definitions of terms, the [OpenAIRE-Glossary](#) can be consulted.

2.2 Open Access requirements in Horizon Europe

Grant Agreement Article 17 describes rules related to dissemination of results and open access to scientific publications and research data. These are outlined below. For further detail see the PDEC Section 9.3.

2.2.1 Obligation to disseminate

Each beneficiary must disseminate their results as soon as possible by disclosing them to the public. However, no dissemination may take place before a decision is made regarding possible protection. Other participants may object if their legitimate interests in relation to their foreground or background could potentially suffer harm.

COMMUNICATION, DISSEMINATION, OPEN SCIENCE AND VISIBILITY (— ARTICLE 17)

Dissemination

Dissemination of results

The beneficiaries must disseminate their results as soon as feasible, in a publicly available format, subject to any restrictions due to the protection of intellectual property, security rules or legitimate interests.

A beneficiary that intends to disseminate its results must give at least 15 days advance notice to the other beneficiaries (unless agreed otherwise), together with sufficient information on the results it will disseminate.

Any other beneficiary may object within (unless agreed otherwise) 15 days of receiving notification, if it can show that its legitimate interests in relation to the results or background would be significantly harmed. In such cases, the results may not be disseminated unless appropriate steps are taken to safeguard those interests.

Additional dissemination obligations

Where the call conditions impose additional dissemination obligations, the beneficiaries must also comply with those.

Figure 2 PREP4BLUE Grant Agreement Article 17 – Annex 5

2.2.2 Open access to scientific publications

Providing open access to publications in Horizon Europe funded projects is an obligation for all grants. Each beneficiary must ensure open access to all peer reviewed scientific publications relating to its results ([GA Article 17 – Annex 5](#)).

Open Science

Open science: open access to scientific publications

The beneficiaries must ensure open access to peer-reviewed scientific publications relating to their results. In particular, they must ensure that:

- at the latest at the time of publication, a machine-readable electronic copy of the published version or the final peer-reviewed manuscript accepted for publication, is deposited in a trusted repository for scientific publications
- immediate open access is provided to the deposited publication via the repository, under the latest available version of the Creative Commons Attribution International Public Licence (CC BY) or a licence with equivalent rights; for monographs and other long-text formats, the licence may exclude commercial uses and derivative works (e.g. CC BY-NC, CC BY-ND) and
- information is given via the repository about any research output or any other tools and instruments needed to validate the conclusions of the scientific publication.

Beneficiaries (or authors) must retain sufficient intellectual property rights to comply with the open access requirements.

Metadata of deposited publications must be open under a Creative Common Public Domain Dedication (CC 0) or equivalent, in line with the FAIR principles (in particular machine-actionable) and provide information at least about the following: publication (author(s), title, date of publication, publication venue); Horizon Europe or Euratom funding; grant project name, acronym and number; licensing terms; persistent identifiers for the publication, the authors involved in the action and, if possible, for their organisations and the grant. Where applicable, the metadata must include persistent identifiers for any research output or any other tools and instruments needed to validate the conclusions of the publication.

Only publication fees in full open access venues for peer-reviewed scientific publications are eligible for reimbursement.

Figure 3: PREP4BLUE Grant Agreement Article 17 – Annex 5

2.2.3 Research Data Management

Managing research data generated in Horizon Europe funded projects is an obligation for all grants. Each beneficiary must ensure research data generated in the project is carefully managed in line with FAIR principles ([AGA Article 17 – Annex 5](#)).

Open science: research data management

The beneficiaries must manage the digital research data generated in the action ('data') responsibly, in line with the FAIR principles and by taking all of the following actions:

- establish a data management plan ('DMP') (and regularly update it)
- as soon as possible and within the deadlines set out in the DMP, deposit the data in a trusted repository; if required in the call conditions, this repository must be federated in the EOSC in compliance with EOSC requirements
- as soon as possible and within the deadlines set out in the DMP, ensure open access — via the repository — to the deposited data, under the latest available version of the Creative Commons Attribution International Public License (CC BY) or Creative Commons Public Domain Dedication (CC 0) or a licence with equivalent rights, following the principle 'as open as possible as closed as necessary', unless providing open access would in particular:
 - be against the beneficiary's legitimate interests, including regarding commercial exploitation, or
 - be contrary to any other constraints, in particular the EU competitive interests or the beneficiary's obligations under this Agreement; if open access is not provided (to some or all data), this must be justified in the DMP
- provide information via the repository about any research output or any other tools and instruments needed to re-use or validate the data.

Metadata of deposited data must be open under a Creative Common Public Domain Dedication (CC 0) or equivalent (to the extent legitimate interests or constraints are safeguarded), in line with the FAIR principles (in particular machine-actionable) and provide information at least about the following: datasets (description, date of deposit, author(s), venue and embargo); Horizon Europe or Euratom funding; grant project name, acronym and number; licensing terms; persistent identifiers for the dataset, the authors involved in the action, and, if possible, for their organisations and the grant. Where applicable, the metadata must include persistent identifiers for related publications and other research outputs.

Figure 4 PREP4BLUE Grant Agreement Article 17 – Annex 5

2.2.4 Obligation and right to use the EU emblem

Partners are obligated to use the EU emblem when publishing and/or presenting work carried out under the PREP4BLUE project (GA Article 17.2). Unless the Agency requests or agrees otherwise or unless it is impossible, any dissemination of results (in any form, including electronic) must display the EU emblem.

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If you have any queries about the use of this disclaimer, please contact ERINN Innovation (cliona@erinn.eu).

2.3 The PREP4BLUE Data Management Plan

The PREP4BLUE Data Management Plan (DMP) aims to provide a strategy for managing background/ data generated and collected during the project and optimise access to and re-use of research data. It is intended to be a 'living' document that will outline how the PREP4BLUE research data will be handled during and after the project, and so it will be reviewed and updated at regular intervals. As detailed above, the DMP is an official project Deliverable (D1.3) due in Month 6 (November 2022); with a DMP Update (D1.7) due in M18 (November 2024) and a Final Report (D1.10) due in M36 (May 2025) but it will also be updated as significant changes arise and periodic reviews at reporting stages of the project will take place to verify the applicability of the DMP to the generated data.

The DMP describes the Research Output Management (ROM) life cycle for datasets based on results from PREP4BLUE. It covers:

- Guiding principles around data management following EC Horizon Europe requirements;
- How to make PREP4BLUE data FAIR: Findable, Accessible, Interoperable and Re-usable;
- Data management cost and allocation of resources;
- Data security and ethics, and confidentiality.

PREP4BLUE will generate diverse outputs, including databases, innovation outputs, new methodologies, data, protocols, experimental approaches and strategies. To integrate the work performed within the different work packages and themes, and to align the scientific tasks with the overarching strategy of the PREP4BLUE project, a structured and efficient Research Output Management is crucial.

The DMP also includes the following annexes which will also evolve over the course of the project:

- Annex 1 consists of useful resources that are relevant to data management to support partners in making their research and data openly accessible in the context of Horizon Europe.
- Annex 2 will be added to the DMP as the project is implemented, and will consist of the PREP4BLUE Inventory of Datasets, and will be generated as and when data is generated and managed.

2.1.1. Data Management Plan Guiding Principles

The Data Management Plan (DMP) of PREP4BLUE is coordinated under WP1, and is articulated around the following key points:

- a) This DMP follows the definition of the **obligations/mandatory practices in the [AGA Article 17 – Annex 5](#)**. The elaboration of the DMP based on these definitions will allow PREP4BLUE partners to address all issues related to IP protection and data in line with the obligations/mandatory practices. The DMP will evolve with the project and will be updated at regular intervals, as and when significant changes arise.
- b) The consortium will **comply with the requirements of Regulation (EU) 2016/679 and of the Council of 27 April 2016 as well as GA Article 14 and 15** on the protection of natural persons with regard to the processing of personal data and on the free movement of such data, and repealing Directive 95/46/EC (General Data Protection Regulation).
- c) **Type of data, storage, confidentiality, ownership, management of intellectual property and access:** Procedures surrounding data collection, storage, access, sharing policies, protection, retention and destruction are in line with EU standards as described in the PREP4BLUE Grant

Agreement (GA) and the Consortium Agreement (CA), particularly GA Article 20.1 Keeping records and supporting documents; GA Article 16 Intellectual Property Rights; GA Article 16.1 Background and access rights to background, especially GA Article 16.2 Ownership of results and GA Article 16.4 Specific rules on IP, results and background; CA Article 8 Results; CA Article 9 Access Rights; CA Article 10 on Confidentiality; and GA Annex I – “Description of the Action”.

2.1.2. PREP4BLUE Research Output Management Policy

As outlined in the executive summary, the collection, organisation, and formatting of data will be the responsibility of the relevant data-owner. Each partner is responsible for their records and documentation in relation to data generated, which must be in line with the accepted standards in the respective field, overseen by Task Leaders. To avoid losses, partners must take measures to ensure that data are backed-up using reliable methods (see 2.1.5 for more on Data Security).

The right of the data owner (members of the research team) to the use of research data is reserved when providing open access. Right to use, here, refers to the right of the data owner to execute the original project plan before opening the data for further use.

All results produced during the project will be assessed for the need of IPR protection by the coordinating team in consultation with the partners concerned. The coordinating team is also responsible for strategic issues, ethics and the exploitation of results, to ensure joint understanding and facilitate creative collaboration (see D1.2 PDEC).

All data underlying peer-reviewed scientific publications must be made openly accessible within and beyond the consortium and uploaded to an open-access repository complying with the FAIR principles within one month of publication, unless it has been evaluated as confidential. The collection and upload of data and underlying publications to the repository is the responsibility of the data-owners.

If data owners wish to restrict access to data that underlies publications, they must provide to the coordinator a ‘justifiable’ reason for doing so as soon as possible and provide evidence of such reason upon prior notice **one month before publication** of the associated peer-reviewed scientific publication. For a list of ‘justifiable’ reasons under EC rules, please see section 2.1.3.2. below.

For each dataset collected, processed and/or generated in the project, the following elements will be documented and reported in the next DMP):

- **Data owner** – Description of the data owner, to include the project partner name, originating work package, task and activity, the responsible researcher(s) name and the primary contact details for enquiries regarding the data.
- **Data Summary**– A description of the data and an overview on how it is being captured and stored, to include the name and description of the dataset, how it is being created and captured, the type and format of the data, the expected overall storage size of the data and whether an IP evaluation is needed.
- **Findability** – Description of domain-relevant repositories, whether the data will be made identifiable by a standard identification mechanism and the type of metadata that will be provided.
- **Accessibility** – Confirmation of whether all data is accessible and the methods or software tools needed to access the data. In cases where it is not accessible a rationale for keeping it restricted must be provided.
- **Interoperability** – Description of whether the data is interoperable and the standard data/metadata vocabularies/ontologies relevant to it.
- **Reusability** – Description of the data licensing, any limits to the re-use of the data and the date (where applicable) the data will be made available for re-use.

- **Allocated resources** – Description of the estimated costs required to make the data FAIR and how these costs will be covered (e.g. covered by work package budget).
- **Security** – Brief description of the data security measures in place, including confirmation of plan for recovery, secure storage and protection over the transfer of sensitive data.
- **Ethics** – Any potential ethical issues must be noted.

A detailed description of the type and format of PREP4BLUE data that will be generated and collected in the PREP4BLUE Data Plan Inventory shared on the PREP4BLUE cloud. The inventory will be shared in the next update of the DMP in M18. Additional datasets may be identified and added to future versions of the DMP as necessary.

2.1.3. FAIR data

In compliance with the Horizon Europe ROM Requirements all PREP4BLUE Data underlying peer-reviewed scientific publications will be 'FAIR', that is **Findable, Accessible, Interoperable and Reusable** (unless there are justified reasons for keeping specific datasets confidential: see section 2.1.3.2.). PREP4BLUE has also aligned its use of data and metadata with the [Ocean Best Practices System \(OBPS\)](#) which provides additional guidance on ocean-specific data and metadata.

2.1.3.1. Making PREP4BLUE Data Findable, including provisions for metadata

PREP4BLUE, will ensure all its data are findable by depositing all project-generated data underlying PREP4BLUE produced, peer-reviewed publications in **open access online repositories**.

Repositories

PREP4BLUE will develop its own database, the Mission Ecosystem Database, which will be made publicly available as well as promoted through the project website. As well as this, PREP4BLUE partners will be asked to select the most appropriate data repositories that facilitate the finding, accessing, re-using and interoperating of data sets, which are the basic principles with which Horizon Europe projects must comply. Among the field-relevant repositories to which it is anticipated that PREP4BLUE will contribute are [INSPIRE](#), [EMODNET](#) and [Copernicus](#). A full list of repositories is described in [Annex I](#). Partners are encouraged to consider the Registry of Research Data Repositories (re3data) and Directory of Open Access Repositories (OpenDOAR) for useful listings of repositories that might be suitable for PREP4BLUE outputs. A PREP4BLUE community page within [Zenodo](#) will also be evaluated as a suitable repository for all project related Open Access publications and datasets.

Identifiers

[Persistent identifiers](#) (PIDs) are important because they unambiguously identify data and facilitate data citation. PREP4BLUE partners will select data repositories that assign a persistent identifier e.g. a Digital Object Identifier (DOI). Partners will also be encouraged to register with ORCID to create a personal professional ID.

Metadata

Metadata is data that provides information about data. The main metadata categories for PREP4BLUE research data are descriptive (title, abstract, author, and keywords, technical characteristics), structural (pages, chapters, tables, pictograms, diagrams) and administrative (file type, permissions, and when and how the file was created). Metadata is as important as the data itself as it allows applications to categorise and archive datasets, facilitating users to easily search and find relevant datasets. For this reason, metadata produced in PREP4BLUE will adhere to the OBPS recommendations on use of common vocabularies.

OpenAIRE is a platform funded and supported by European Commission with the mission to shift scholarly communication towards openness and transparency and facilitate innovative ways to

communicate and monitor research. **Each dataset owner will ensure that their chosen repositories disseminate (meta)data to OpenAIRE to maximise data sharing, finding and re-use of research outputs from PREP4BLUE.** Any repository that is listed in this DMP is interoperable with OpenAIRE; partners who wish to use a different repository may make an inquiry to the Coordinating Team to check whether it disseminates to OpenAIRE. If it does not, the Coordinating Team may contact OpenAIRE to see whether it can be added.

As the project progresses and datasets are identified and collected, further information on specification of standards for metadata creation will be outlined in subsequent versions of the DMP. Information on naming conventions used, approach towards search key words, approach for clear versioning, and making data findable and crosslinked will also be provided.

2.1.3.2. Data Sharing: Making PREP4BLUE Data Openly Accessible

To encourage **re-use and further application** of project results, all PREP4BLUE **data** underlying peer-reviewed scientific publications will be made available via open access platforms for verification and re-use, unless the data-owner can justify why data cannot be made openly accessible. The Coordinating Team will assess such justifications and make the final decision, based on the [permitted exceptions for underlying data²](#) and examination of the following elements regarding confidentiality of datasets:

- i. Commercial sensitivity of datasets
- ii. Priority to exploitation, protection of IPR, security and privacy rules
- iii. Conflicts between open-access rules and national and European legislation (e.g. data protection regulations).
- iv. Sharing data would jeopardise the aims of the project
- v. Other legitimate reasons, to be validated by the Coordinating Team

When considering the potential to make data open access, partners are requested to review the project **Consortium Agreement** and the **IP protection guidelines (D1.2 PDEC)**. These documents define the main approach regarding the ownership, protection and access to key knowledge like IP and data. This approach will allow the PREP4BLUE partners, collectively and individually, to pursue opportunities arising from the project's results.

As the project progresses and data are identified and collected, further information on making data openly accessible will be outlined in subsequent versions of the DMP. Specifically, information on methods or software tools needed to access the data, information on where data and associated metadata, documentation and code are deposited and how access will be provided in case there are restrictions.

2.1.3.3. Making PREP4BLUE Data Interoperable

Interoperable data allows exchange and re-use between researchers, institutions, organisations, countries, etc. (i.e. adhering to standards for formats, as much as possible compliant with available (open) software applications, and in particular facilitating re-combinations with different datasets from different origins).

² Exceptions to open access to research data underlying publications in the Open Research Europe are permitted according to the relevant policy of Horizon Europe. These consider the obligation to protect results, confidentiality obligations, security obligations, the obligation to protect personal data and other legitimate constraints. Where open access is not provided to the data needed to validate the conclusions of a publication that reports original results, authors should provide the relevant access needed to validate the conclusions to the extent their legitimate interests or constraints are safeguarded (see [Add a Data Availability Statement to Your Article](#)).

Project partners should consider from the outset identifying the most suitable file types and structures they can utilise to support external interoperability once published. Specifically, this includes what tools will be needed to validate the results, e.g. specialised software or software code, algorithms and analysis protocols. Where possible, partners should provide these instruments themselves alongside the open access dataset.

Partners must select repositories which observe Ocean Best Practices and OpenAIRE guidelines for interoperability, including OBPS standards for data and metadata generation, storage, labelling and transfer and OpenAIRE guidelines for data archives. These guidelines can be found online (<https://www.oceanbestpractices.org/> and <https://guidelines.openaire.eu/en/latest/>).

As the project progresses and data are identified and collected, further information on making data interoperable will be outlined in subsequent versions of the DMP. Specifically, information on data and metadata vocabularies, standards or methodologies to follow to facilitate interoperability and whether the project uses standard vocabulary for all data types present to allow interdisciplinary interoperability.

2.1.3.4. Ensuring PREP4BLUE Data Re-Use

Horizon EU GA clearly states the licensing it mandates for datasets and their metadata: CCBY CCBO.

2.1.4. Allocation of Resources

Costs related to open access of research data in Horizon Europe are eligible under the conditions defined in the PREP4BLUE Grant Agreement (GA), in particular Article 6 – Eligible and Ineligible Costs, such as Article 6.2.C.3 – Other goods works and services, but also other articles relevant for the cost category chosen. These include the costs of data deposit, long-term storage and cost in time and effort needed to prepare the data for sharing and preservation.

Costs cannot be claimed retrospectively. Project partners will be responsible for including any relevant costs in their financial statements.

2.1.5. Data Security

Storage systems that meet the needs of the project will need to be considered. Partners must use multiple methods to backup and copy research data and **protect data from unauthorised access or use or from disclosure**. All partners should consult with their organisation IT professionals to set up and manage data security and make sure the right safeguards are in place. Partners should also consider that data files may need encrypting before storage or transfer and take the appropriate steps to ensure its security.

Long-term data management primarily addresses security in relation to where the data will be kept, and how it will be accessible after the research project is complete. Partners must ensure that data are stored in certified repositories for long-term (a minimum of five years after the end of the project) preservation and curation.

2.1.6. Ethics and Confidentiality

PREP4BLUE ensures compliance with the ethical commitments set in GA Article 14 in the Task 1.1, to ensure that ethical requirements are met for all research undertaken in the project, including data management aspects, in compliance with Horizon Europe ethical standards. PREP4BLUE partners must comply with the ethical principles (see GA Article 14) and confidentiality (see CA Article 10).

ANNEXES

Annex I – Online Open-Access Resources & Useful Links

Oceanographic specific best practices

- <https://www.oceanbestpractices.org/>
- <https://www.bodc.ac.uk/resources/vocabularies/>

Open Science in Horizon Europe

- Open Science: <https://openscience.eu>
- Open Research Europe: <https://open-research-europe.ec.europa.eu/>

FAIR Findable (repositories)

- Directory of Open-Access Repositories: <http://www.opendoar.org/>
- Registry of Research Data Repositories: <https://www.re3data.org/>
- ZENODO Open-Access Data Repository: <https://zenodo.org/>
- INSPIRE: <https://inspire.ec.europa.eu/>
- EMODNET: <https://emodnet.eu/en>
- Copernicus: <https://www.copernicus.eu/en/library>
- Horizon Results Platform (HRP) [Horizon Results Platform \(europa.eu\)](https://horizonresultsplatform.europa.eu/)
- The official portal for European data: <https://data.europa.eu/en>
- European Open science Cloud: <https://eosc-portal.eu/>

FAIR: Findable (Identifiers)

- Making Data ‘Findable’ using Persistent Identifiers: <https://www.openaire.eu/how-to-make-your-data-fair>
- Using Identifiers for Open Access- for Authors and Research Materials: http://ec.europa.eu/information_society/newsroom/cf/dae/document.cfm?action=display&doc_id=4607

FAIR: Findable (Metadata)

- Oceanographic specific vocabularies for metadata: <https://www.bodc.ac.uk/resources/vocabularies/>
- Explanations of Scientific Metadata: <http://www.dcc.ac.uk/resources/curation-reference-manual/chapters-production/scientific-metadata>
- Metadata Standards Directory Working Group: <http://rd-alliance.github.io/metadata-directory/>
- Open Data and Metadata Standards: https://joinup.ec.europa.eu/sites/default/files/document/2015-05/d2.1.2_training_module_2.2_open_data_quality_v1.00_en.pdf
- Use of DataCite for metadata provisions: https://guidelines.openaire.eu/en/latest/data/use_of_datacite.html

FAIR: Interoperable

- OpenAIRE Guidelines for Literature Repositories, Data Archives, and CRIS Managers based on CERIF-XML: <https://guidelines.openaire.eu/en/latest/>

FAIR: Reusable (licensing)

- Creative Commons licensing : <https://creativecommons.org/licenses/>
- Advice on commercialisation of research data: <https://eudat.eu/data-access-and-re-use>
- Licensing Wizard: <https://b2share.eudat.eu/>
- IPR Helpdesk Advice on seeking IP Professionals: <https://www.iprhelpdesk.eu/sites/default/files/documents/Guide-IP-professionals.pdf>
- IPR Helpdesk Factsheet on IPR Valuation: <https://www.iprhelpdesk.eu/sites/default/files/newsdocuments/Fact-Sheet-IP-Valuation.pdf>